

Probability Related to Conservation of Energy/Momentum and Quantum Mechanics

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The Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) probability $p(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$ yields the probability to find a particle with energy e_i in an ideal gas at temperature T . Nevertheless, this probability may be derived strictly through considerations of conservation of energy, i.e. two body elastic collisions using $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$ and $p(e_1)p(e_2)=p(e_3)p(e_4)$. In other words, the probability $p(e_i)$, i.e. the presence of an e_i particle, is linked to the probability for a reaction to occur. We argue, however, that one may introduce probability based on the conservation of energy $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$ without having an equilibrium distribution of e_i particles. In particular, if a single e_1 particle collides with a single e_2 particle, one does not know the outcome except that energy must be conserved if the collision is elastic.

This leads to the idea of assigning probability to the various e_i, e_j outcome pairs. The least information scenario suggests that one use an AND probability $p_1(e_i)p_1(e_j)$ (here we use p_1 to distinguish it from the MB p) and argue that $p_1(e_i)p_1(e_j)=\text{constant}$ for any $e_i+e_j=E$. This implies that $p_1(e_i) = \exp(C_1 e_i)$. If C is real, however, there is a problem because the single incoming e_1 and e_2 should also be associated with a probability p_1 and there is no distribution of a total amount of energy here. This suggests that C_1 might be purely imaginary, i.e. iC_1 . A similar argument may then be applied to momentum (assume one dimension for simplicity), which would then lead to a probability p_1 of $\exp(i C_2 p)$. The problem with this expression is that momentum, unlike energy, is a vector. Even in one dimension, one has p and $-p$ and the probability cannot be different because one does not know what co-ordinate system is being used (i.e. in which direction the x-axis points, to the right or left).

. Probability should be independent of the co-ordinate system, we argue. This means that in a vector case, one needs to multiply p by a linear quantity which represents a change measured according to the co-ordinate axis, in particular Δx . Then, p and Δx or $-p$ and $-\Delta x$ account for the two types of one -dimensional co-ordinate axes and $\exp(i p \Delta x)$ is the same for both. This suggests that one may have co-ordinate axes changes beyond simply $x \rightarrow -x$. In particular, one may consider a Lorentz transformation and the invariant $-Et+px$. It then seems that conservation of e and p probabilities are linked to this invariant and should be $\exp(-iEt)$ and $\exp(ipx)$ respectively. This then leads to the notion of free particle quantum mechanics.

Maxwell-Boltzmann Distribution and Conservation of Energy

The Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution $p(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$ may be obtained through maximization of entropy - $\sum_i p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i))$ subject to the two constraints $\sum_i p(e_i)=1$ and $\sum_i e_i p(e_i)$. Alternatively, it may be derived by considering reaction balance linked to elastic collisions, i.e. conservation of energy:

$$E_1+e_2 = e_3 + e_4 \quad ((1a)) \quad \text{and} \quad p(e_1)p(e_2) = p(e_3)p(e_4) \quad ((1b))$$

Thus, even though one has a gas with total energy E and this energy is partitioned to N single particles, leading to $p(e_i)$, the probability for two particles with e_1, e_2 to collide is $p(e_1)p(e_2)$ and

this must equal $p(e_i)p(e_j)$ for any $e_i+e_j=e_1+e_2$, if one has a minimal information scenario. The notion of conservation of energy seems to be key in developing the probability $p(e_i)$.

We suggest that conservation of energy (and also momentum) exists for free particles as well. At first one might think that these are not associated with probability, but we try to argue to the contrary.

Free Particle Energy and Momentum Conservation and Probability

Consider a single particle with energy e_1 colliding elastically with a particle with e_2 . One may try to consider the outcome in terms of probabilities and may suggest the least information approach. In such a case, one would suggest that:

$$p_1(e_3)p_1(e_4) = p_1(e_i)p_1(e_j) \text{ for any } e_i+e_j=e_3+e_4=e_1+e_2 \quad ((2))$$

In other words, one assumes that same probability for any e_i, e_j pair of outcomes that satisfy ((2)).

We use p_1 to distinguish this probability from the MB $p(e_i)$. This suggests a power law just like the MB case:

$$p_1(e_i) = \exp(C e_i) \quad ((3))$$

The problem is that there is no ideal gas with distributed energy here. If e_3 and e_4 are linked with a p_1 probability, then the single e_1 and e_2 particles should also be linked to a p_1 probability, but they are deterministic particles. Thus, one may argue for:

$$C = i C_1 \text{ where } C_1 \text{ is real} \quad ((4))$$

In other words, one might suggest a purely imaginary probability such that its magnitude is the same for e_1 and e_2 .

If this same reasoning is applied to momentum (consider 1-dimension for simplicity) then

$$p_1(p) = \exp(i C_1 p) \quad ((5))$$

The problem with ((5)) is that p is a vector and so takes on two values, p and $-p$. These depend on the co-ordinate axis, i.e. the direction in which the x-axis points. A probability, however, should not depend on the co-ordinate axes, we argue. This leads to a problem. One needs to multiply p by a linear quantity linked to the measure of the co-ordinate axis, i.e. Δx .

Then: p and Δx for one co-ordinate axis become $-p$ and $-\Delta x$ for a reversed co-ordinate axis, but:

$$\exp(i p \Delta x) \quad ((6)) \text{ remains the same.}$$

If one can consider reversed co-ordinate axes, one should consider more general transformations of axes. This we argue leads to the notion of special relativity.

Special Relativity

Special relativity represents transformed co-ordinate axes and yields the invariant:

$$-Et + px \quad ((6))$$

Px or $p \Delta x$ is already consistent with the quantity we suggested above. Thus, we propose that one use:

$$\exp(-iEt) \text{ and } \exp(i px) \quad ((7))$$

to describe free particle probabilities which ensure conservation of energy and momentum (when required).

Noether's Theorem and $\exp(ipx)$

Noether's theorem suggests that for a given invariance, there exists a corresponding conserved quantity. For $\exp(ipx)$, p (x-component of momentum) is conserved if p if x is invariant, i.e the particle is moving through uniform space. One may obtain the value of p from $\exp(ipx)$ by using the operator $-i\partial/\partial x$.

Probability and Δt , Δx Intervals

We suggested the form $\exp(-iEt) \exp(ipx)$, especially the $\exp(ipx)$ form, due to changes in co-ordinate axes leaving probability invariant. These forms, however, suggest that:

$$P_1 \Delta x_1 = P_2 \Delta x_2 \text{ or } p_1 = \hbar/\Delta x_1 \text{ or } \Delta x_1 = \text{wavelength} = \hbar/p \quad ((8))$$

if one wishes to have the same probability for different p_1 values. In other words, p_1 is associated with a specific length in space (the wavelength \hbar/p_1). This is required in order to have the notion of probability remain invariant to co-ordinate axes changes and to have a probability consistent with conservation of momentum/energy. Probability appears in the first place because one argues that one does not know the outcome of collisions, only that conservation occurs.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we note that an ideal gas represents a distribution of total energy among N particles, leading to the notion of $p(e_i)$, i.e the probability to find a particle with energy e_i . On the other hand, one has elastic two body collisions and if one assumes that an e_1, e_2 collision can

lead to e_i, e_j outcomes with equal probability if $e_i + e_j = e_1 + e_2$, then $p(e_1)p(e_2) = p(e_i)p(e_j)$ or $p(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$, the Maxwell-Boltzmann result.

We ask: What happens if one has two particles with e_1 and e_2 that collide elastically? One does not know the outcome and may assume equal probability to have any e_i, e_j pair if $e_i + e_j = e_1 + e_2$. In this case, however, there is no real-valued $p(e_i)$ because one does not have an ideal gas case, i.e. there is no distribution of energy. Nevertheless, one may write: $p_1(e_i)p_1(e_j) = \text{constant}$ for any outcome. This result, however, implies that $p_1(e_1)p_1(e_2) = p_1(e_i)p_1(e_j)$ and that the incoming free particles are linked with probability, although not a real valued one, it seems.

One may suggest a purely imaginary probability $\exp(i e_i \text{ constant})$ which upholds conservation of energy. This notion may be applied to momentum (consider 1-dimension) i.e. $\exp(i c^2 p)$. The problem is that one has p and $-p$ and these are based on the co-ordinate axis. One cannot have two different values of probability for p and $-p$ based on a co-ordinate axis we argue. Probability should be independent of the co-ordinate axis direction. Thus, we propose that one multiply p by a linear measure of the direction of the co-ordinate axis, i.e. Δx . Then $p, \Delta x$ for one co-ordinate axis direction yields the same probability for $-p, -\Delta x$.

One may generalize this to other co-ordinate axis transformations, namely the Lorentz one which has the invariant $-Et + px$. This suggests using $\exp(-iEt)$ and $\exp(ipx)$, the quantum free particle probabilities which are introduced because one does not know the exact outcome of a collision with conserved energy and momentum.